

ABRASIVE PROCESSES OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Static and dynamic indentation of homogeneous solids are now well-known. Their modelisation allows a good prediction for abrasive processes using the rupture mechanic theory and plasticity theory. An experimental methodology, sclerometric pendular and linear tests, is used here in order to study the abrasive processes of composite materials. The abrasive scratch morphology depends on the mechanical behaviour of each constituent : fibres, matrix and interfaces. Model materials are tested. The results show that abrasive processes of composite materials lead to complex phenomena, and the models established in case of homogeneous solids are insufficient to give a good prediction to the different observations. Results of sclerometric tests reveal effects of the different constituents: ductile matrix, brittle fibre yarns and adhesion at interfaces.

INTRODUCTION

Erosion and abrasion are forms of wear characterized by the scratching of surfaces. Scratching produces either brittle scratches with material removal by a fracture process or ductile scratches with plastic cutting and deformation. For semi-brittle materials, a transition scratching depth h from ductile to brittle abrasion can be observed [1], using a pendular sclerometer to perform single tip abrasion under controlled conditions (fig.1). This transition h is characterized by the onset of lateral cracking : material removal rate is then very high in comparison with ductile cutting processes. This transition is particularly important in abrasion or erosion of brittle or semi-brittle homogeneous surfaces.

Knowledge of the rheological parameters : hardness H , toughness K_C ,

ratio H/K_C , and their variations with speed can lead to the understanding and the prediction of the behaviour of semi-brittle materials in an abrasive environment : the transition scratching depth h is in fact connected to the ration $(H/K_C)^m$ with $1,5 < m < 2$ [2].

Figure 1. The scratching apparatus

A similar experimental procedure is used here for composite material.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

- Pendular scratching tests

The composite material tested is a tridirectional carbon-carbon composite. This material consists of carbon fibre yarns periodically, tridirectionally arranged (fig.2). The carbon fibre yarns are made with 2 or 4 strands containing about 3000 filaments. The carbon matrix fills up the voids between the fibre yarns.

This material is used as a model material : Owing to its macroscopic structure the morphology of the abrasive scratch can be easily observed. On another hand, its local and global mechanical behaviour are particularly well-known [3], [4] under static loading :

- transversal properties of fibre yarns are isotropic ; their behaviour is elastic, linear, with a brittle rupture ;
- interfaces behaviour is elastic with damage ;

- properties of matrix blocks are isotropic ; their behaviour is elasto-plastic with damage.

Figure 2. Geometrical structure of 3D carbon-carbon

The results of pendular scratching tests are as follows :

The ductile behaviour of matrix blocks and the brittle behaviour of fibre yarns are confirmed. A transition depth can be observed for the fibre yarns, with lateral brittle chipping (fig.3) . The scratching process leads to the destruction and the breaking up of the interfaces, these phenomena seem predominant in case of lateral chipping.

These observations are in agreement with the different basic abrasion processes observed in case of homogeneous materials. In addition, the interfaces behaviour appears as an important phenomenon. Rheological parameters H , K_C , are difficult to define with such anisotropical and heterogeneous materials. Consequently, further experiments were conducted in order to have a better understanding of the different effects : influence of each constituent and interface effect.

Figure 3. Pendular scratching behaviour of 3D c-c

– Linear scratching test

This test was built up in order to determine the local properties of each constituent. An abrasive tip scratches on horizontal specimen (fig.4) under controlled conditions (depth and velocity of the scratch). The tangential force is recorded by measuring the elongation of the spring K during scratching.

Figure 4.

Linear scratching test

Spherical and conical indenters are used. The scratching depth is varied from 0.05 mm to 0.15 mm. The speed of the abrasive tip can be varied from .1 to 4 mm/s. The same carbon-carbon composite material is tested. Basic recording of F_t (tangential force versus time) are shown fig. 5.

Figure 5. Tangential force during a scratch with 3D c-c
5a : spherical tip, 5b : conical tip

On fig. 5a, a spherical tip is used. The tangential force displays fluctuations. During rubbing, there is no tearing of the surface at the rear of the indenter. Only a slight plastic deformation of the surface occurs. The value of the tangential force depends on the constituent in contact :

F_t min is connected with rubbing of the fibre yarns

F_t max is connected with rubbing of the matrix blocks.

These results emphasize effects of the shear stress s of the contact.

On fig. 5b, a conical tip is used. The evolution of the tangential force displays also fluctuations. The largest period corresponds to scratching

of the different constituents.

The scratching process is in fact different from one constituent to one other :

- fibre yarns display brittle scratching with lateral chipping (F_t min).
- matrix blocks lead to ductile grooving (F_t max).

These observations emphasize effects of the bulk properties of different constituents (ductile or brittle) in abrasion of the composite materials.

On another hand, the scratching process is disturbed when the indenter crosses the interfaces between constituents : the breaking up of the interfaces is similar to that observed with pendular scratching tests (fig.3).

This phenomenon leads to some disturbance of the tangential force, more difficult to analyse.

CONCLUSION

Abrasive processes of composite materials appears as a mixture of different basic abrasion behaviour : ductile grooving and brittle scratching. The abrasive behaviour of each constituent can be predict using rheological parameters, however present results emphasize that damage conditions at the interfaces are one of the most important phenomena. The understanding of abrasive processes of composite materials greatly depends on the knowledge of the adhesive properties between matrix and reinforcement. Fine sclerometric tests appear to be useful to analyse these different effects.

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